

CHARACTERISATION OF MICRO-MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF THERMAL BONDED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Amit Rawal¹ and Rajesh Anandjiwala^{1,2}

¹*National Fibre, Textile & Clothing Centre, M&MTek, CSIR, Port Elizabeth 6000, South Africa*

²*Department of Textile Science, School of Science, Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University, Port Elizabeth 6000, South Africa*

SUMMARY: Thermal bonded structures have a range of applications which include geotextiles, interlinings, carpet backing and as reinforcements in composites. In this paper, the micro-mechanical models for thermal bonded composite nonwoven structures have been developed by incorporating geometrical and mechanical properties of the constituent fibres. The theoretical models have been validated with experimental results. The effects of lapping angle and curl factor have also been studied. The distribution of fibre orientation within a nonwoven structure has been expressed using Fourier series. Our models will help in designing the nonwoven composites for specific end uses.

KEYWORDS: thermal bonding, modelling, curl factor, fibre orientation, lapping angle, viscoelastic.

INTRODUCTION

Thermal bonding has emerged as an important nonwoven web bonding process which is utilized for a wide range of applications in thermoplastic and thermoset composites. Thermal bonding is a two step process, namely, web laying and bonding the fibres by applying thermal energy. The process exploits low melt thermoplastic fibres acting as the binder material to fuse the normal fibre matrix. Therefore, thermal bonded nonwoven structures are essentially bonded fibre networks which can be utilized as reinforcing media in composite materials. Due to the ease of production and economics, now-a-days such nonwoven materials are widely utilised in moulded thermoplastic fibre reinforced composites for automotive, construction, marine, electronics and engineering applications. The mechanical response, fracture and cracking of such reinforced composites are governed by the properties of the reinforcing medium, polymer matrix and the inter-laminar region responsible for interfacial adhesion. The deformation of nonwoven under defined mechanical loading conditions involves several mechanisms, such as elongation, bending, buckling, shear and breakage of fibres at the micro level. The modelling of tensile deformation of thermal bonded nonwovens is complex due to the simultaneous existence and interaction of these basic mechanisms.

Backer and Petterson [1] carried out a pioneering work on fibre network theory for predicting the tensile properties of a thermal bonded nonwoven structure based on the assumption that fibre segments between bonds are straight. Hearle and Stevenson [2, 3] expanded their theory by incorporating the effect of fibre curl. Winchester and Whitwell [4] made a significant contribution by measuring the thermal bonded web responses to variations in base fibre, binder, web formation and bonding conditions and developed models for these response. Later, Hearle and Ozsanlav [5] predicted stress-strain curves of various nonwoven structures

with known fibre parameters, such as fibre strength, fibre orientation and fibre curl. In addition, computer models have been developed to predict the mechanical properties of nonwovens [6-8]. Gilmore et al. [9] developed a computational model incorporating the effects of fabric-failure mechanism and fibre-orientation distribution for predicting the load-deformation of thermal point bonded structures. A comprehensive review on the structure and properties of thermal bonded structures indicates a lack of experimental validation of these models [10]. A semi-empirical model has been developed to predict the strength of thermal point bonded fabrics; however, the effect of fibre curl was neglected in this analysis [11]. Furthermore, Adanur and Liao [12] predicted the tensile behaviour of nonwoven fabrics from the fibre arrangement characteristics. The models have been validated for spun bonded and needlepunched nonwovens. In the current paper, one of the objectives is to utilise these models to predict the mechanical response of thermal bonded nonwoven composite structures.

THEORETICAL

Micro-Mechanics of Nonwoven Structures

In this study, the nonwoven structure is composed of cross-laid web structures formed by a carded web traversed back and forth on to a moving belt and the resultant material contains two or more layers disposed at angles $+\alpha$ and $-\alpha$ to the machine direction. The lapping angle, α , with respect to cross-machine direction can be calculated using the following relation:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{v_{mb}}{v_{cl}} \quad (1)$$

where, v_{mb} and v_{cl} are linear speeds of moving belt and cross-lapper in m/min, respectively.

The variation in the lapping angle between the web layers imparts different mechanical and structural characteristics to the nonwoven structure. The nonwoven properties are also influenced by the geometrical properties of fibre such as curl in a fibre segment, orientation, etc. The fibre curl factor, C , is defined as the extent of curvature as given below:

$$C(\%) = \frac{L_c - L_s}{L_s} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where, L_c and L_s are the curve and straight lengths defined between two points. In a fibrous web, the curl factor varies widely as shown in Fig. 1a and therefore it is expressed in terms of curl factor distribution, $D(C_i)$. It is defined as the ratio of the relative frequency of the fibres having curl factor, C_i , to the total number of the fibres in a web. Fig. 1a shows the schematics of the variation in the fibre curl in a typical fibrous web. The curl factor is the highest in fibre segment A based upon the fact that the number of waves per unit length is maximum. However, the fibre segment E is straight and has a zero curl factor. On applying the load, fibre segment E would initially act as a load bearing element. Later, fibre segment D would be straightened and begin to bear the stress. Therefore, all the fibres having variation in curl factor value would experience different amount of stress. It is also possible that some of the fibres which are not held by the bonds, as shown in Fig. 1b, may not be able to share the load, even at maximum stress, or the transfer of stress in such loosely held fibres between the bonds may occur due to inter-fibre friction mechanism. Such fibres may exhibit the curl factor exceeding the breaking extension of the fabric and the effect can be different depending upon the amount of inter-fibre friction resulting from the transverse pressure within the fibre network.

The stress-strain model was developed by incorporating the fibre curl factor and the following assumptions were made:

- There is an uniform distribution of fibre and bond segments in each layer of the web.

- The frictional effects between the fibres are neglected. Hence the fibres not held by bonds do not contribute to the tensile behaviour of fabric.
- The mechanical behaviour of nonwoven structure can be described as visco-elastic [13]. The fibre segments and bond points can be modelled as a series of ideal elastic spring and ideal viscous dashpots, respectively. This means the effects of the bonds are not included and therefore, the bond acts as a rigid joint between the fibre segments.

We assume that the stress (σ) - strain (ϵ_f) behaviour of the fibre is nonlinear, i.e. $\sigma = f(\epsilon_f)$. Following the methodology proposed by Adanur and Liao [12] the fibre stress can be expressed in terms of web strain, ϵ , by incorporating the curl factor as shown below:

$$\sigma = f\left(\frac{100}{100 + C_i}(\epsilon - C_i)\right) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: Curl in (a) web (b) typical fibre

Considering that there are N number of fibres in the web, the web stress $F_i(\epsilon)$ can be given as

$$F_i(\epsilon) = N \cdot D(C_i) \cdot f\left(\frac{100}{100 + C_i}(\epsilon - C_i)\right) \quad (4)$$

By definition,

$$D(C_i) = \frac{y_i}{N} \quad (5)$$

where, y_i is the relative frequency of the fibres having curl factor C_i .

From Eqns. 4 & 5, we get

$$F_i(\epsilon) = y_i \cdot f\left(\frac{100}{100 + C_i}(\epsilon - C_i)\right) \quad (6)$$

The function $f(\frac{100}{100+C_i}(\epsilon - C_i))$ can be defined in fourth order polynomial stress-strain relation of the fibres. Furthermore, the above relation can be modified for a blend of n number of fibre types.

$$F_i(\epsilon) = y_{i1}f_1(\frac{100}{100+C_{i1}}(\epsilon - C_{i1})) + \dots + y_{in}f_n(\frac{100}{100+C_{in}}(\epsilon - C_{in})) \quad (7)$$

Eqn. 7 can be further simplified by assuming the equal proportion of the fibres having the same curl factor in the blend of fibres. For example, in a thermal bonded structure consisting of blend of low melt thermoplastic and matrix fibres, the web stress can be defined as:

$$F_i(\epsilon) = \frac{y_i}{2} \left[f_1(\frac{100}{100+C_i}(\epsilon - C_i)) + f_2(\frac{100}{100+C_i}(\epsilon - C_i)) \right] \quad (8)$$

EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS

Five thermal bonded composite structures were produced from 50:50 % blend of low-melt (melting temperature -110^0C) and normal (melting temperature -250^0C) polyester fibres. These composite structures are produced by varying lapping angles, namely, 5^0 , 10^0 , 15^0 , 20^0 and 25^0 , as shown in Table 1. The stress-strain curves of 20 cm x100 cm fabric strips were tested on Instron Tensile testing machine under uniaxial loading at a strain rate of 100 mm/min in the machine and the cross-machine directions [14]. The stress-strain curves of low-melt and normal polyester fibres are also measured (shown in Fig. 2) by standard test method [15]. The fibre orientation and curl factor are digitally measured and captured using image analysis program, ‘analySIS’ version 3.2. The histograms and fitted curves of the relative frequency of fibres for 10^0 orientation angle interval with respect to the cross-machine direction are computed. The relative frequency of the fibre curl is shown in Fig. 3 for all thermal bonded nonwoven composite structures investigated in this study.

Table 1: Production of nonwovens by varying the speeds of moving belt and cross-lapper

Lapping Angle (0)	Velocity of Moving Belt (m/min)	Velocity of Cross-lapper (m/min)
5	1.84	21
10	3.7	21
15	5.63	21
20	5.9	16.22
25	7.5	16.22

Fig.2: Stress-strain behaviour of normal and low melt polyester fibres

Fig.3: Curl factor distribution in a thermal bonded composite web

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Lapping Angle & Curl Factor

As shown in Table 1 higher lapping angles of 20 and 25 degrees are obtained by increasing the speed of the moving belt and simultaneously decreasing the speed of the cross-lapper. In general, with the increase in lapping angle the tensile strength of fabric decreases as shown in Fig. 4. As the lapping angle increases, the number of fibrous layers in a composite web reduces which results in reduction of strength as shown in Fig. 4. However, the breaking strength of nonwovens produced at 15° lapping angle is less than the corresponding structure formed at 20°. This is attributed to the high proportion of curled fibres in the nonwoven

produced at 15° lapping angle as shown in Fig. 3. The contribution of the fibres in sharing the load would be initiated at a later stage. Similar effect can be observed for a thermal bonded composite produced at 10° lapping angle as shown in Fig. 4. Furthermore, the stress-strain behaviour of thermal bonded composite structures has been predicted from Eqn. 8 and compared with the experimental results. Fig. 5 shows a typical comparison between the predicted and experimental stress-strain curve for thermal bonded composite produced at 5° lapping angle in the machine direction.

Fig. 4: Stress-strain curves of nonwoven fabrics at various lapping angles (machine direction)

Fig. 5: Stress-strain curve of nonwoven at 5° lapping angle in machine direction

In general, the predicted stress – strain curve is consistent with the experimental curve. The shift in the starting position of the predicted stress-strain curve is due to our assumption of equal curl factor for both types of fibres. However, it may be possible that the curl factor is relatively low either in low melt or normal fibres resulting in an overall decrease in the curl factor of the web. The initial modulus and breaking strength are similar in both the experiment and predicted curves. The stress-strain properties were also measured for

nonwoven structures in the cross-machine direction. The ratio of breaking strength in cross-machine (BXMD) to machine directions (BMD) has been compared with the lapping angle as shown in Fig. 6. The anisotropy in strength of the nonwoven fabric decreases with the increase in lapping angle as shown in Fig. 6. It was found that isotropy in tensile strength can be obtained in the structures produced at higher lapping angles.

Fig. 6: Relation between the breaking strengths ratio with lapping angle.

Fibre Orientation Angle

In a cross-laid web, the fibre orientation is defined as an angle formed between the tangent to the curl and the cross-machine direction, denoted by θ , as shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Fibre Orientation

Furthermore, the fibres distributed within the nonwoven structure can be expressed in terms of Fourier series as given below.

$$y(\theta) = a_0 + b_k \cos(k\theta \pm \alpha) \quad (9)$$

where, $y(\theta)$ is the relative frequency at an orientation angle, θ , n is number of intervals, k is any positive integer and a_0 and b_k are defined as follows:

$$a_0 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n} \text{ and } b_k = \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \cos k\theta, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$$

Fig. 8 shows a typical fitted Fourier curve for the measured relative frequency of the fibres of nonwovens produced at a 5° lapping angle.

Fig.8: Orientation distribution of the nonwoven produced at 5° lapping angle

Table 2 shows Fourier coefficients for the Eqn. 9 and a good correlation between the measured and predicted relative frequencies is evident. The effect of lapping angle was also analysed on the fibre orientation as shown in Fig. 9. There is no discernible relation between the lapping angle and fibre orientation as there is no perceptible change in the shape of the curves.

Table 2: Fourier and Correlation Coefficients for nonwovens

Coefficients	5° Lapping Angle	10° Lapping Angle	15° Lapping Angle	20° Lapping Angle	25° Lapping Angle
a_0	5.56	5.56	5.56	5.56	5.56
b_1	-0.8	-0.09	-0.61	-0.49	-0.5
b_2	2.57	1.531	1.761	1.873	1.68
b_3	-1.3	-0.42	-0.8	-1.01	-1.39
b_4	-1.3	-1.59	-1.56	-1.87	-1.7
b_5	-0.4	-0.46	-0.26	0.332	-0.22
b_6	0.38	0.328	0.909	-0.13	0.612
b_7	-0.6	-0.86	-0.81	-0.64	-0.61
b_8	-0.8	-0.84	-0.66	-0.34	-0.24
b_9	-0.5	-0.02	0.22	-0.05	-0.4
b_{10}	-0.8	-0.54	-0.14	0.094	-0.16
b_{11}	-0.5	-0.12	-1.11	-0.44	-0.75
b_{12}	0.19	3E-15	-0.38	-0.38	0.174
b_{13}	0.09	-0.17	-0.95	-0.29	-0.28
b_{14}	-0.1	-0.61	0.034	0.321	-0.07
Correlation Coefficient (R)	0.89	0.87	0.85	0.80	0.80

Fig.9: Effect of lapping angle on fibre orientation

CONCLUSIONS

The micro-mechanical behaviour of thermal bonded composite structures have been analysed based upon the methodology proposed by Adanur and Liao [12]. The model includes the effect of the geometrical disposition of fibres, i.e. curl factor, on the nonwoven composite structures. The theoretical models of stress-strain curves have also been validated with the experimental results. The curl factor distribution affects the shape of the stress-strain curve including the breaking strength of nonwoven composite structures investigated. The combined effect of lapping angle and curl factor was also investigated and it was found that nonwoven composite structures with isotropic strength can be produced at higher lapping angles (about 20°). Furthermore, the effect of lapping on the fibre orientation distribution is insignificant. The distribution of fibre orientation within a nonwoven structure has been successfully expressed using Fourier series.

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